

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTANGIBLE ASSETS ON THE PERFORMANCES OF A BUSINESS

Jaborova Kumush Shoymardon qizi

Graduate Student of Termiz State University

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Abstract

This article is based on the assumption that there is a strong influence between the intangible assets on the financial value and the performance of a business. This is more obvious especially in the case of the businesses which require a considerable creativity or are science-based.

Keywords: Intangible assets, financial value, business, goodwill, trademark, brand, financial market, investor confidence, IAS 38.

Introduction

Generally speaking, intangible assets are very valuable for any company as these help in differentiating products or services, building customer loyalty, and establishing a competitive advantage in the market. A century ago, John Stuart, the president of Quaker Oats Company, an American food conglomerate based in Chicago, made the following statement: "If the businesses were to be split up, I would be glad to take the brands, trademarks, and goodwill, and you could have all the bricks and mortar and I would be better than you". In this regard, he had expressed his interest in things that were familiar from an investment and accounting perspective, and the difference between book and market value, and were capitalized as "intangible assets and goodwill"¹ As you know, intangible assets are type of non-physical [assets](#) that cannot be seen or touched but have value for a business or organization. For example, patents, trademarks, copyrights, [goodwill](#), brand recognition, and [intellectual property](#) are its examples. These are difficult to be valued, as their worth is based on subjective factors such as reputation and market demand. However, they can be extremely valuable to a [company](#), as they can help to differentiate its products or services, build customer loyalty, and establish a competitive advantage in the financial market. So that, intangible assets have a significant role in helping businesses succeed. Here are some reasons that make them important:

Competitive advantage: Assets, such as trademarks and patents, can help a business differentiate its products or services from those of competitors, giving it a competitive advantage in the market.

¹Diefenbach, 2004, p. 554

Brand recognition: Assets, such as brand names and logos, can help to build brand recognition and customer loyalty, which can be critical for long-term success.

Innovation: Assets, such as patents and copyrights, can encourage innovation by protecting the ideas and inventions of businesses and individuals, providing an incentive for continued investment in research and development.

Revenue generation: Some assets, such as licensing agreements and royalty streams, can generate significant revenue for a business without requiring a physical product or service.

Investor confidence: The presence of valuable assets on a company's balance sheet can signal to investors that the business has a strong foundation and potential for long-term success, increasing investor confidence and attracting additional investment.

Furthermore, researchers found that intangible assets as a proxy for innovation have a significant impact on the market value of the company, emphasizing that the critical value of intangible assets is 1% of total assets. When intangible assets exceed this value, the value of the firm also increases significantly. Moreover, companies with higher investments in intangible assets achieve higher profitability². In order to make informed decisions about the future strategic direction of an organization, to challenge strategic assumptions and to continuously learn and improve, it is critical to understand the drivers of performance and competitive advantage. Intangible assets may be key drivers of future performance and sustainable competitive advantage. Therefore, organizations require mechanisms that allow them to assess their intangible value drivers.

Conclusion.

Businesses must understand the importance of their intangible assets and the role that they play in driving the business forward, as well as the need to prioritize a thorough protection strategy to prevent valuable information loss. For instance, the objective of IAS 38 is to prescribe the accounting treatment for intangible assets that are not dealt with specifically in another IFRS. The probability recognition criterion is always considered to be satisfied for intangible assets that are acquired separately or in a business combination³.

There is a presumption that the fair value of an intangible asset acquired in a business combination can be measured reliably. An expenditure on an intangible

² Economic and business review journal, September 2022

³ IAS 38 Intangible Assets issued, 31 March 2004

item that does not meet both the definition of and recognition criteria for an intangible asset should form part of the amount attributed to the goodwill recognized at the acquisition date.

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